

The Problem of Child Labour in Indian Society

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Abstract

The problem of child labour in India is a clear violation of social, economic and human rights. Poverty, illiteracy, indebtedness and social inequality are prevalent in many families in India, be it rural or urban. And this leads to millions of children working in various industrial, domestic and informal sectors, depriving them of their right to education, health and a safe childhood. According to the 2011 census, an estimated 10.12 million children in the age group of 5–14 were engaged in child labour, which seriously affects their physical, mental and intellectual development. Article 24 of the Indian Constitution prohibits child labour and Article 21A ensures the right to education. Efforts are also made to protect child rights through the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act 2016, the RTE Act 2009, the Juvenile Justice Act and international treaties. However, despite the laws, child rights continue to be exploited in many places. Although many schemes to eradicate child labor are being touted at the government level, the reality is different.

Child labor is a direct assault on the human rights of children—their right to protection from exploitation, right to education, right to health, and right to dignity are being denied. Therefore, this problem can only be solved through joint efforts of the government, society, family, and NGOs. It is imperative that citizens themselves come forward to raise their voices against child labor and protect child rights, because a safe, dignified, and educational childhood for every child is the fundamental foundation for a bright future for the country.

A proportion of children in India are engaged in child labour. In 2011, the national census of India found the total number of child labourers (age 5–14) to be 10.12 million, out of the total of 259.64 million children in that age group.^[2] The child labour problem is not unique to India; worldwide, about 217 million children work, many full-time.

Introduction

The problem of child labour in India is not just a social or economic issue but a serious human rights violation. According to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the provisions of the Indian Constitution, every child has the right to education, health, protection and a safe childhood. However, in reality, many children are forced to work due to poverty, illiteracy, social inequality, indebtedness, family circumstances and organized exploitation. Although children under the age of 14 are legally prohibited from working in hazardous industries in India, millions of children work for low wages in brick kilns, tea houses, domestic work, agriculture, factories, construction sector and the informal economy. This causes

them physical, mental, social and educational harm and seriously affects their overall development.

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Current (2024-2025) definitive statistics on child labour in India are not readily available, as the latest official nationwide data is based on the 2011 census. However, various reports and surveys provide the following information:

According to the 2011 census: The total number of child labourers in India between the ages of 5 and 14 was estimated at 101 million (10.1 million).

- UNICEF Report (2024): Based on data analysis of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) and the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) in 2018-19, the estimated number of child labourers in India is between 1.8 million (1.8 lakh) and 3.3 million (3.3 lakh).
- International Labour Organization (ILO) and UNICEF Global Estimates (2024): Globally, about 138 million children are engaged in child labour, of which 54 million are engaged in hazardous work. India has the highest number of child labourers in the South Asian region.

Article 24 of the Indian Constitution explicitly prohibits child labour, while Article 21A guarantees the right to education. In addition, the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act 2016, the Juvenile Justice Act, the RTE Act 2009, as well as national and international policies are working to protect child rights. The problem of child labour cannot be solved by laws alone; it can only be overcome by the collective efforts of society, family, government and NGOs. From a human rights perspective, every child must have a safe, dignified and educationally enriched childhood — because today's children are tomorrow's responsible citizens. Thus, the issue of child labour is a critical issue for India's social progress and effective action on it is an important step towards protecting human rights.

Top 5 States In Child Labour, 2009-10

If we look at the overall situation of child labour in India, if we look at the number of child labourers working in various sectors in Uttar Pradesh, it is seen that approximately 1.7 million children are working in very hazardous conditions. This is followed by West Bengal and Rajasthan, although the estimated number of children working in Uttar Pradesh is three times that of West Bengal, there are more and more child labourers in different states.

Across the country, 50% of the children working in various sectors are rural boys in the age group of 5-14, while rural women are 35%. In Bihar, more than 81% of the working children are rural boys, while in Jharkhand, 77% of the children are rural boys. In Tamil Nadu, 80% of the working children are rural girls and it is a dangerous reality that they are forced to work in dirty fields.

Notably, children in urban areas are better off in terms of child labour. 85% of the working children in the country are rural children, so it can be said that these children are largely deprived of education and health in rural and urban areas.

Child labour in India is a serious problem that exploits children and violates their human rights. This problem arises due to poverty, unemployment and lack of education, which force children to work. Child labour endangers the physical, mental and emotional health of children and negatively affects their bright future. . At an age when boys and girls should be seen holding books, pens, pencils, baskets, shovels, hammers, washing utensils, hotel towels, shoe polish brushes, etc., most children are seen holding baskets, shovels, hammers, washing utensils, hotel towels, shoe polish brushes. The number of children in India involved in child labour is . In 2011, the National Census of India found that out of a total of 259.64 million children in that age group, 10.12 million were child labourers in the age group [5-14]. All this must change. For this, the Government of India has made it clear that we are bound by the Convention on the Rights of the Child by signing the U.N.O. The government has implemented various schemes to prevent child labor today. Various laws have also been made regarding the exploitation of child rights. However, today it is seen that child labor and child rights are being exploited in most places. Today, there is

a need for citizens to take the initiative themselves to eliminate this inhumanity of child rights exploitation. Human rights will not be violated with the initiative of citizens.

Human Rights

Human rights are acquired by humans at birth. The right/right to live like a human being in life is human rights or human rights. It is only by acquiring this right that a person can achieve his own all-round progress and personality development. The Constitution of India has given the citizens of this country the right to seek justice against injustice, the right to freely adopt a religion, the right to own property, the right to express his thoughts, the right to freely engage in a profession, the right to education, the right to equality, etc. Due to these rights, a person can live a happy and contented life.

*Child labour is a prevalent problem in India, and it is a severe violation of human rights. Millions of children in India are forced to work in hazardous and exploitative conditions, depriving them of their childhood, education, and basic rights. The issue of child labour in India has received widespread attention from international organizations, civil society, and the government. Despite the efforts to combat child labour, the problem persists, and children continue to suffer. This research article aims to provide an analysis of child labour and human rights violations in India. Moreover, this article attempts to provide the strategies for combating child labour and upholding human rights in India. (**Child Labour And Human Rights Violations In India: An Analysis** -Preety Gupta, Dr. Arsheed Ahmad Ganie Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, IEC University, Baddi, Himachal Pradesh)*

Child Labour and Human Rights

- **Exploitation and Abuse:** Child labourers are often victims of physical, sexual and emotional exploitation. They have to work for very low wages, in extremely dangerous and slave-like conditions.
- **Right to Education and Development:** Child labour deprives children of their right to education. They do not get the opportunity to go to school, which hinders their all-round development.
- **Impact on Health:** Harsh working conditions increase the risk of serious diseases such as malnutrition, mental health problems and addiction in children.
- **Right to Dignity:** Child labour deprives children of their dignity and childhood, which are essential for their development and survival.

Child Rights -

The Constitution of India grants children the right to a name, nationality. It provides rights such as the right to justice against neglect and exploitation, the right to life and development, freedom of expression, the right to freedom of religion, etc.

What is child labour?

Generally, the age up to 14 years is the age of play and growth. Children of this age who have to do physical work to satisfy their hunger are called child laborers. Hoyer Folk, Chairman of the United States Child Labor Committee, has defined child labor as 'any work done by children that interferes with their physical development, educational advancement, and recreation'.

The children born in this country are a national asset, but this national asset is seen as highly neglected and suffering from problems like malnutrition. Children do not seem to be getting the minimum family and support they need to become healthy and productive citizens of the country. About 80% of child labourers in India are employed in the agricultural sector. Certain types of work, including debt bondage, commercial sex work, and recruitment into the armed forces, are considered inherently dangerous for children. The NSSO report for 2017-18 indicates that 95% of children in the age group of 6-13 years are attending educational institutions, while the proportion of children in the age group of 14-17 years is 79.6%. Therefore, a large number of children in India remain vulnerable,

Reasons for the rise of child labor

1. **Poverty** Poverty is widespread in India. Due to the poor financial situation of the family, children have to work to support the family. Even today, 35% of the population in India is living below the poverty line. Even if the adults in these families work full-time, they cannot support all their family members with the income they receive. As a result, the adults in such families force even the young children in their families to work.
2. **Inflation** - Today, inflation has increased tremendously, due to which it has become difficult for the poor to live. Due to increasing inflation, even the essential needs of the poor are not met. Result: The head of the family uses even the young children in his family as laborers to support all the family members.
3. **Addiction in the family** Today, the rate of addiction among family members has increased tremendously. Therefore, the family cannot support itself with the meager money they receive. Therefore, the child of the family is forced to work as a wage laborer at a young age.
4. **Home industries were closed down** In the past, some home industries were done at home. From those home industries, enough income was earned to support the family members. But these home industries were closed down due to the industrial revolution. Due to this, many families faced hunger. To stop this hunger, the head of the family also takes the young children of the family out for labor. This is why child labor emerged.
5. **Indebtedness** Due to low wages, the head of the family often has to take out loans to meet the needs of the family. Due to this, he becomes in debt. To pay off the loan taken and its

interest, the head of the family forces the young children of the family to work as wage laborers, which is why the problem of child labor arises.

6. The situation in the society is no longer the same as before. Orphanage In the case of some children, their parents have died while they were still in their infancy. Due to this, those children are destined to be orphans. Such orphaned children do not get help from anyone. As a result, such a boy works as a manual labourer in a factory, hotel, agricultural business, etc. to earn a living. Due to such orphanhood, child labourers emerge.
7. The door of social inequality in the society has not yet been closed, so many children do not get the opportunity to study, so they get trapped in the cycle of child labor. Lack of education Even today, not everyone in our country understands the importance of education. Even today, most of the citizens and their children are far from education, they are illiterate. Due to ignorance of education, they do not get government jobs and employment opportunities. As a result, such people have no option but to do wage labor to feed their stomachs. Therefore, child laborers work in various fields.

Present day the numbers of child working population are increasing day by day in the developing and under developed countries. Actually the child working populations are called as child labour whose age ranged from 5 to 14 years. In India, the children are engaged mostly in various low-key jobs of the unorganized sectors which are hazardous in situation (Bhupen Barman)

Effects of the child labor problem

- 1) Children who do physical labor around the age of 14 are child laborers. At this age, they are ignorant and the employers harass them by forcing them into work and paying them low wages.
- 2) The age of 14 is the age of playing, entertainment and increasing their IQ through education. But at this age, child laborers have to do hard and laborious work. Due to this, their personality development is stunted.
- 3) Child laborers have to do hard work at a young age. Due to this, their physical health is affected and they become weak and frail.
- 4) The condition of child laborers is 'hard work, low wages'. Due to this low wages, they do not get healthy and sufficient food daily. Result: Malnutrition problem arises.

SOLUTION TO ELIMINATE CHILD LABOR

- Since the problem of child labor arises from poverty, the government needs to make efforts to eradicate poverty and implement them properly.
- If the government curbs inflation, the problem of child labor will disappear.
- The government/non-governmental organizations, wise citizens should search for orphaned children and solve the problems of their livelihood, shelter, and health.

- Since the problem of child labor arises only due to illiteracy, the government should implement the concept of 'Sab Padhe-Sab Badhe'.
- The employers, industrialists, manufacturers, etc. who employ child labor should be punished.
- Young children are the wealth of the country. They are the future of the country. It is necessary to create awareness in the society that no one should employ such children.
- The government should make efforts to eliminate unemployment.
- The government should implement the 'Earn and Learn' policy,
- The Child Rights Act should be strictly implemented.
- The government should provide incentives to people working on child rights.
- Illiterate parents should be provided with adult education opportunities and they should be made aware of the ill effects of addiction.
- Child laborers should be made aware of their exploitation

Conclusion

The problem of child labour in India is a major challenge to the social, economic and human development of the country. Due to poverty, illiteracy, indebtedness, addiction and social inequality, millions of children are still deprived of education and are forced to work in hard and unsafe jobs. Despite the rights of the child in the Constitution, various laws, schemes and international agreements, the exploitation of child labour continues in many places, which is a serious violation of human rights. Child labour has a negative impact on the physical, mental health, dignity and personality development of children. Therefore, this problem will not be solved by laws alone; it is only through the collective efforts of the government, society, NGOs, families and every conscious citizen that children can be given a safe, dignified and educational childhood. Since the protection and development of children is the foundation of the bright future of the country, the elimination of child labour is an essential and indispensable duty for the promotion of human rights.

Child labour, child labour laws or schemes have not been effectively implemented. There does not seem to be any awareness in society regarding child labour. The problem of child labor has become a complex one. To solve this problem, it is necessary to strictly implement the Child Rights Act without any loopholes. The media must play an important role in making the government and the employers aware of the ill effects of child labor. Since this problem is basically related to illiteracy and poverty, effective efforts should be made to eradicate literacy and poverty. By curbing the demon of inflation, this problem can be eliminated to a large extent. The government and voluntary members should take the initiative and accept the guardianship of child laborers. Only then can this problem be eliminated.

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